

Analysis of Product and Service Quality, as Well as Price Perception of the Acepresso Brand on Repurchase Intention Mediated by Customer Satisfaction (Case Study of ACEpresso Brand at Kawan Lama Building)

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Abstract:- Using information from a customer survey at ACEpresso in the Kawan Lama Building, this study examines the connections between product quality, service quality, price perception, customer satisfaction, and repurchase plans in the Indonesian coffee industry. The findings demonstrate that consumer satisfaction is positively and significantly impacted by both product and service quality, but not by price perception. Additionally, customer satisfaction serves as a mediator between product quality and service quality and repurchase intentions and has a positive and significant impact on repurchase intentions. These results offer Indonesian coffee companies useful information on how to raise client satisfaction levels and encourage repeat business.

Keywords:- Service Quality, Product Quality, Price Perception, Customer Satisfaction, Re-Purchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ever since the Dutch introduced coffee from Malabar, India, to Java in 1696, coffee has been popular in India. Coffee is an invigorating drink that, thanks to its caffeine content, can easily keep the drinker awake. In addition to caffeine, coffee also has antioxidants that nourish the body and tannin compounds that give it a distinctive aroma. Until now, coffee has become one of the most consumed drinks in the world. [35].

The consumption of coffee is increasing in Indonesia. According to estimates from the Ministry of Agriculture, the amount of coffee consumed nationally increased from 250,000 tons in 2016 to 276,000 tons in 2017, a 10.54 percent rise. Between 2016 and 2021, coffee usage in Indonesia is anticipated to rise by an average of 8.22% annually. In 2021, there should be a coffee surplus of 425,000 tons with a production of 774,600 tons and a usage of 370,000 tons. [18].

Java Island in particular is widely recognized as the home of coffee. The majority of Indonesia's coffee-growing territory is located on the island of Sumatra, which makes up more than 60% of the nation. The majority of the coffee produced in Indonesia is cultivated on smallholder plantations that are dispersed throughout the major coffee-producing islands of Sumatra, Java, Flores, and Bali. Robusta beans, which have a lower market value than Arabica beans, make up more than 70% of the coffee produced in Indonesia. In addition to being

used to make instant coffee, espresso, and coffee blends, Robusta coffee beans are renowned for their bitter and strong taste. In the past, Indonesia has primarily sold its coffee exports to countries like the United States, Italy, and Malaysia. However, the country's coffee exports are beginning to suffer from changes in local consumption habits. In recent years, Indonesia has increased its annual coffee output. But domestic coffee usage has increased as well. It is predicted that by 2019, domestic demand will outpace coffee exports, leading to worries about a worldwide coffee shortage. [37]

July 2021 was the starting point of ACEpresso's operations at Kawan Lama Office Building. At the beginning of sales it generated sales of 250 million sales in a month and seeing sales in the following months there was a significant increase in sales but there was a decrease in sales in the last 2 months due to unpredictable weather. Based on the sales data above, researchers are interested in examining what is behind consumer intentions whether to repurchase the product. As ACEpresso is a new player in this business field. [1]

Repurchase intention refers to a customer's desire or intention to repurchase a specific product or a group of products related to the product they have purchased. Repurchase plans are influenced by a number of factors, including brand image, customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, and product attributes. [Customer satisfaction is one of the mediating factors with the greatest influence on repurchase intentions. The level of customer satisfaction determines how happy they are with the product they get and how likely they are to repurchase it. There is a large body of literature exploring and analyzing the effect of product and service quality on customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions. Product quality and service quality have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions, according to previous studies. [14]

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior is all forms of a person's psychological actions and processes that control them before making a purchase, using a product, and evaluating the product. Consumer behavior is also defined as a study of a person's purchasing decision process which includes the function of a product, service, and idea. [39].

B. Theory of Planned Behavior

Theory to explore a person's behavioral intentions towards various things, such as purchasing, using goods and services, and so on, which are based on and controlled by several things, such as attitude, social norms, subjective norms, and perceptions of something that also control [19]

C. Continuance Intention Theory

A theoretical model used to explain why customers continue to use a product or service, despite alternatives. Affective attachment refers to the emotional attachment or loyalty that customers have towards a product or brand. These three factors are interrelated, and together they contribute to overall customer satisfaction and continuance intention. Variables supporting Continuance Intention Theory include service quality, product quality, price perception and customer satisfaction [45].

D. Re-purchase Intention

Repurchase Intention is the tendency of behavioral actions to carry out repurchase activities, and get a good or positive response to actions that occurred in the past [34].

E. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a behavior so that customers get the maximum pleasant experience by minimizing unpleasant customer experiences [40].

F. Product Quality

A product with the best specifications available to satisfy customer requirements is said to have high product quality. One of the characteristics of the product is also referred to as the producer's understanding of something that can be marketed with the intention of satisfying requirements. This product's quality can also be seen, appreciated, and bought to satisfy requirements. Therefore, product quality is a collection of product attributes that help the product fulfill predetermined demand objectives [8].

G. Service Quality

Service Quality can be interpreted as one of the many important factors that become consumers' intention to make repeat purchases because service quality is the expectation of consumers in return for the services they have issued [29].

H. Price Perception

Price perceptions influence purchasing decisions because the price of the product offered is considered affordable by consumers with good product quality. Consumers feel confident and satisfied to buy. Brand image and price perception provide enough confidence for consumers to buy their products [44].

Fig 1. Framework

In accordance with the formulation of the problem, theoretical studies, previous research, and framework, the hypothesis in this study is:

- H1 : Product Quality has a positive and significant effect to Customer Satisfaction.
- H2 : Service Quality has a positive and significant effect to Customer Satisfaction.
- H3 : Price Perception has a positive and significant effect to Customer Satisfaction.
- H4 : Customer Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Re-purchased Intention.
- H5 : Customer Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Product Quality and Re-purchased Intention.
- H6 : Customer Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Service Quality and Re-purchased Intention.
- H7 : Customer Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Price Perception and Re-purchased Intention.

III. METHODOLOGY RESEARCH

A. Research Design

The research design is research that studies the cause-and-effect relationship between two or more variables. This is a quantitative research that uses statistical calculations and SmartPLS 3.2.9 software and Microsoft Excel to analyze the relationship between variables and test hypotheses. SmartPLS uses SEM techniques to enable the analysis of causal relationships between variables [43].

Table 1. Operational Variable

No.	Variables	Indicator	Scale
1	<i>Re-purchased Intention (Y2)</i> (Goldsmith, R.E., Lafferty, B.A. and Newell, S.J. 2000) and (Oliver, R. L. 1980)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A person's tendency to repurchase a product. 2. A person's tendency to refer to others. 3. One's tendency to explore 4. The behavior of a person who has a primary preference for a product. This preference can only be changed if something happens to the preferred product. 	Likert
2	<i>Customer Satisfaction (Y1)</i> (Daryanto and Ismanto 2014)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Consumers will feel satisfied if the results of their evaluation show that the product used is of high quality. 2. Consumers will feel proud and gain confidence that others will admire them when using products with certain brands that tend to have a high level of satisfaction. 3. Cost and convenience Consumers who do not need to pay additional costs or do not need to waste time to get a product or service tend to be satisfied with it. product or service 	Likert
3	<i>Product Quality (X1)</i> (Gani & Hillebrandes Oroh, 2021)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Performance of the product itself 2. Expertise created on the product itself 3. Durability of the product 4. Product appeal 	Likert
4	<i>Service Quality (X2)</i> (Gani & Hillebrandes Oroh, 2021)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Relating to physical facilities. 2. Provide fast service response. 3. The attention the company gives to customers. 4. The ability of employees to instill customer trust. 5. The size of the company is able to provide services in accordance with customer expectations related to physical facilities. 	Likert
5	<i>Price Perception (X3)</i> (Umbola et al., 2019)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Affordable price 2. Promo price that attractive such as discounts, free shipping 3. Price match with quality 4. Payment method 	Likert

B. Data Collection Methods

The method used in this study to collect data is an online questionnaire with a google form to obtain data from ACEPresso consumers who have made purchases to answer several indicators of the research variables. In this study, researchers took advantage of office breaks to collect data by sitting in the coffee shop and looking for respondents to fill out a google form by first asking respondents who had bought ACEPresso coffee more than twice then after the questionnaire was filled in the respondent's answer would be scored using a scale called Likert. Where this Likert scale can be interpreted as a level of value that is planned to analyze how strongly the subject agrees to something. The statement on the scale has five points with the following instructions: 1 for strongly disagree, 2 for disagree, 3 for disagree, 4 for agree, and 5 for strongly agree.

C. Population

As mentioned above, the respondents taken in this study are employees of Kawan Lama Building who have started making repeat purchases from ACEPresso coffee shops. Purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique, was used in this sampling methodology to ensure that the data is representative of the population. The minimum sample size when using Purposive Sampling Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is 100 respondents. The researcher used the hair formula to determine the number of samples to be used, choosing 5 to 10 of the total number of indicators. As a result, there were approximately 114 responses to the survey questions.

D. Data Analysis Method

A structural equation model (SEM) built on partial least squares is used to examine the relationships among the model's variables, including those between indicators and constructs and those between constructs, in order to test the research hypothesis. T-statistics and path coefficient analysis methods are used to test the study's hypothesis. If the number range for the path coefficient is between 0.000 and 1.96, the value is deemed acceptable. These two figures can be used to decide whether or not to accept the study hypothesis.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study, data was obtained by distributing questionnaires so that 121 answers were obtained from respondents who had made repeat purchases at ACEPresso coffee shops. It is known that the male gender is more of an audience who buys ACEPresso products as many as 64 respondents or 53%. Meanwhile, the women who are the audience who buy ACEPresso products are quite a large percentage, namely 58 respondents or 47%, and are dominated by ages 21-30 years, namely 70 respondents or 58%

A. Descriptive Analysis of Questionnaire Answer Results

➤ Product Quality

The average result for questionnaire statements on the Product Quality variable (X_1) is 3.69, which in general can be said that product quality here is quite important to consumers. The indicator $X_{1.2}$ has the highest average of 3.74 from the variable stating that according to respondents the barista's expertise is very good at making ACEPresso coffee

preparations so that the coffee served feels different.

➤ *Service Quality*

The average result for questionnaire statements on the Service Quality variable (X_2) is 3.96, which in general can be said that service quality here is an important indicator for consumers. The $X_{2,2}, X_{2,3}, X_{2,5}$ indicator has the highest average of 3.98 from the variable stating that according to the respondents, they feel comfortable and the service provided by the baristas is good because of their dexterity so that the service expected by consumers is good. Achieved according to consumer expectations.

➤ *Price Perception*

The average result for questionnaire statements on the Price Perception variable (X_3) is 3.99, which in general can be said that price is an important thing in this study. This shows that the $X_{3,4}$ indicator has the highest average of 4.08 from the variable stating that respondents feel facilitated by the payment system offered, namely cashless payments or using QRIS, E-Money, and Debit.

➤ *Customer Satisfaction*

The average result for the questionnaire statement on the customer satisfaction variable (Y_1) is 3.74, which in general can be said that customer satisfaction is important in selling this product. The indicator $Y_{1,1}$ has the highest average of 3.9 from the variable stating that respondents are satisfied buying ACEpresso products because of the quality of this product.

➤ *Repurchase Intention*

The average result for questionnaire statements on the Repurchase Intention variable (Y_2) is 3.64, which in general can be said that consumer repurchase interest here is quite important in this study. The $Y_{2,2}$ indicator has the highest average of 3.69 of the variable states that respondents are happy to refer ACEpresso products to friends around the company

B. Convergent Validity

This number represents the factor loading for the latent variable and its associated signs. As a result, the number used to assess a construct's validity is its convergent validity value. With a limit of 0.5 in this research, indicators with a factor model value above 0.5 are recognized as valid.

As seen in the image above, the factor model number for each item is greater than 0.5. In order to validate these products. The idea that measurements of a concept should be highly correlated can be used to determine the convergent validity test..

A. Discriminant Validity

The Cross Loading value of all variables in this research model has a value above 0.7. So the researcher concluded that Discriminant Validity has met the requirements.

B. AVE Testing Results

The results of the AVE value are above the limitations of 0.50, and therefore all variables in the study are deemed to be valid. Whereas client satisfaction is 0.732, price perception is 0.827, service quality is 0.817, product quality is 0.772, and repurchase intention is 0.758.

C. Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

This method compares the correlations between each construct's square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) with the associations between other constructs in the model to assess discriminant validity. According to this study's AVE root test, the model has a good level of discriminant validity.

D. Heterotrait-Monotriat Ratio Of Correlations (HTMT)

The component correlation is estimated by the HTMT (more precisely, an upper bound). HTMT must be significantly 0.9 in order to differentiate between two factors with clarity. The test findings in this study indicate that all HTMT values can be stated to indicate that all constructs are valid in discriminant validity based on the calculation of HTMT.

E. Multicollinearity Test

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) number can be used to determine whether a regression model contains multicollinearity. If the independent variables have a higher correlation, the VIF number will be higher. The absence of multicollinearity is indicated by a VIF number of <10. Based on the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test findings, it can be concluded that all constructs are valid and there is no multicollinearity because all VIF values are <10.

F. R-Square

According to the study's findings, the customer happiness variable's (Y_1) R-Square is 0.393. This R-Square number indicates that only 39.3% of the variation in the Customer Satisfaction construct can be accounted for by the variation in the Product Quality, Service Quality, and Price Perception constructs; the remaining 60.7% is accounted for by factors other than those under study. The Re-purchased Desire (Y_2) variable's R-square value is 0.305. According to this R-Square value, customer satisfaction variability accounts for 30.5% of the variability of the repurchased intention construct, with the remaining 69.5% being explained by factors outside the scope of the research. With this, the impact can be described as moderate. The more the independent variable can describe the dependent variable, the better the structural equation, and this is indicated by the R-Square number.

Fig 2. Convergent Validity Test Model

G. Coefisien of Determinaion f-Square (f^2).

Based on the research results, the value of f^2 can be stated that the Product Quality variable on the Customer Satisfaction variable produces a value of f^2 of 0.169, so the effect is classified as moderate. The Service Quality variable on the Customer Satisfaction variable produces an f^2 value of 0.157, so the effect is classified as moderate. The Price Perception variable on the Customer Satisfaction variable produces an f^2 value of 0.000, so its effect is classified as low. While the performance variable Customer Satisfaction on the variable Re-purchased intention f^2 value of 0.439, then the influence is high.

H. Test Predictive Relevance Value (Q-Square)

Based on the results of this study, the results of the Cross-validated Redundancy Test can be explained that the Q value² is 0.266 and 0.224. Because the value is greater than 0, the model has predictive relevance.

I. Hypothesis Test

The path coefficients, which display the parameter coefficient and the t-statistic significance value, are used to evaluate hypotheses. If the t-statistic value of the effect is higher than the t-table or the P value is less than 0.05, the impact between the variables is deemed significant. The PLS SEM system itself created a method for testing the mediation effect, which is a process where variable X influences variable Y through variable Z. We examine whether variable X influences variable Y through variable Z in the mediation test. In the mediation test, we test whether the relationship between X and Y is explained by variable Z. In the PLS SEM system, the mediation test is conducted by comparing the model that includes the direct relationship between X and Y with the model that includes the relationship between X, Z, and Y, where the effect of exogenous variables on the mediating variable and must be significant at the t-statistic. > 1.96 and p value <0.05 then it is declared significant.

Fig 3. Influence Test Models

The t-statistic value must be tested in addition to the path coefficient value in order to approve or reject the hypothesis. If the t-statistics > t table value, the hypothesis is adopted.

Table 2. Path Coefficients Analysis

	Hipotesis	Original Sample	t- Statistics	P values	Keterangan
H1	Product Quality	0,339	3,084	0,002	Positive Significant
	→ Customer Satisfaction				
H2	Service Quality	0,404	3,320	0,001	Positive Significant
	→ Customer Satisfaction				
H3	Price Perception	0,017	0,156	0,876	No Significant
	→ Customer Satisfaction				
H4	Customer Satisfaction	0,552	0,5	0,000	Positive Significant
	→ Re-purchased Intention				
H5	Product Quality	0,187	3,374	0,001	Positive Significant
	→ Customer Satisfaction				
	→ Re-purchased Intention				
H6	Service Quality	0,223	2,358	0,019	Positive Significant
	→ Customer Satisfaction				
	→ Re-purchased Intention				
H7	Price Perception	0,010	0,159	0,874	No Significant
	→ Customer Satisfaction				
	→ Re-purchased Intention				

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

In this research, it was discovered that while price perception had no significant impact, product and service quality had a positive and significant impact on customer satisfaction. The results are in line with previous research on this issue. In the context of the coffee shop business, providing high-quality products and services is essential to retain and attract customers. To achieve this, coffee shops can focus on offering unique blends, using high-quality coffee beans, providing detailed information about coffee, and creating a cozy atmosphere. In addition, training staff to provide excellent service and continuously monitoring and improving service quality can help increase customer satisfaction.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the introduction, discussion in the previous chapter and the results of the discussion analysis regarding "Analysis of Product Quality, Service Quality, and Price Perception on Re-purchased Intention with Mediation Customer Satisfaction", the authors draw the following conclusions:

- Product Quality has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.
- Service Quality has a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.
- Price Perception has no significant effect on Customer Satisfaction
- Customer Satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on Re purchased Intention Customer Satisfaction.
- Customer Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Product Quality and Re-purchased Intention.
- Customer Satisfaction mediates the relationship between Service Quality and Re-purchased Intention.
- Customer Satisfaction does not mediate the relationship between Price Perception and Re-purchased Intention

According to the analysis's findings, while price perception is not a significant factor in determining customer satisfaction, product quality and service quality are significant factors because they positively impact customer satisfaction.

Customer satisfaction is the primary factor influencing repeat purchase intentions. In addition, customer satisfaction mediates the connection between repeat purchase intentions and the quality of the product and the service.

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